

Reflection on the Importance of Hand Care of Medical Care Personnel Under COVID-19 Pandemic

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Xi Gao^{*}, Linna Luo[†], Li Lu[‡], Weiwei Liu[§]

ABSTRACT

Hand hygiene is one of the most cost effective ways to prevent and control hospital infections. Health care providers have to follow the five hand washing moments even more strictly in the case of COVID-19. However, with frequent cleaning and disinfection, the skin barrier will be damaged to some extent and the skin will become dry, rough and fragile due to over degreasing. Without timely and proper care and moisturizing, it is likely to cause skin diseases and increase the risk of infection. This paper summarizes the importance and necessity of hand care of health care providers through an investigation of the damage caused to hand skin by frequent hand washing and the effects of moisturizing on skin barrier.

INTRODUCTION

Hand hygiene has always been the most effective, economical and important method in preventing and controlling cross-infections involved in healthcare in various health care institutions (Neesha, 2020). The COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China, in 2019, has swept the whole country and even the whole world with its menacing power. Some of the medical workers were infected with novel Coronavirus while wearing masks and protective clothing. Therefore, some experts speculated that novel Coronavirus may have infected them through skin and mucosa. Skin is the first barrier against viruses. Medical workers in dermatology have the responsibility to enhance their understanding of the role of skin in the prevention and control of hospital infections, and give full play to their expertise to help combat the epidemic.

LITERATURE

Skin is the largest organ of the human body and an important physiological defending line against external stimuli. Skin barrier from a macroscopic perspective is composed of the skin's own cell structure, the microorganisms on the skin surface and the skin's immune system. Internally, skin barrier can prevent the loss of skin moisture and nutrients and maintain the stability of the skin's internal environment. Externally it can protect against the stimulation of environmental toxins, allergens, pathogens and other physical and photochemical stimulations present in the external environment. It can even directly kill the invading pathogenic microorganisms to maintain the normal function of the body. The stratum corneum (SC) plays the most important role of infiltration and physiological barrier in the skin barrier. The barrier function of SC is significantly related to

* Dermatology department of University-Town Hospital of Chongqing Medical University/CHINA

† Emergency department, ICU of University-Town Hospital of Chongqing Medical University/CHINA

‡ School of Public Health and Management, Chongqing Medical University, Chongqing/CHINA

§ School of Public Health and Management, Chongqing Medical University, Chongqing/CHINA

keratinocytes, intercellular lipids, natural moisturizing factors and skin metabolites. The condition in which the skin maintains a slightly acidic PH (4.6-5.8) also has important effects on the synthesis of intercellular lipids, the function of the skin surface barrier, and the microbiome Giovana, G. M., et. al. (2017), Johannes, W., et. al. (2018), Jürgen, B., et. al. (2018).

RESEARCH

Purpose of the research

The aim of this research is to prevent of cross-infection in health care institutions has become the focus of patient safety with one of the most critical measures being hand hygiene María B., et. al. (2019). Some scholars have pointed out that infection, especially in health care institutions, is an important factor leading to the death of the elderly. Studies have shown that poor hand hygiene of medical workers can lead to intraoperative infections in patients, and surgical site infection accounts for a significant proportion of healthcare related infections (>1/3) David B. J., et. al. (2019).

Method of Research

In this study, hypoallergenic ingredients and possible adverse effects encountered with moisturizers were considered. Although the importance of hand hygiene in the prevention of healthcare related infections has been explicitly emphasized worldwide, hand hygiene compliance among medical workers remains poor Qian, Z., et. al. (2018), Tartari E., et. al. (2019). According to the evaluation results of hand hygiene facilities and staff compliance in a large tertiary healthcare institution in Nigeria, the hand hygiene facilities and hand hygiene compliance among medical workers in this institution are quite disappointing Kenneth I., et. al. (2019). Low hand hygiene compliance is closely related to the high workload, inadequate time, inadequate hand hygiene facilities, lack of learning resources for hand hygiene or forgetfulness of medical workers Tartari E., et. al. (2019). Studies have also shown that frequent hand washing or alcohol-based disinfection can damage the hand skin barrier of medical workers, causing them to have negative neurosensory reactions such as tingling and desquamation and thus further reducing their compliance with hand hygiene Qian, Z., et. al. (2018), Tartari E., et. al. (2019), Kenneth I., et. al. (2019), Maryam S., et. al. (2019) David B. J., et. al. (2019). During the preventive period of the global pandemic, low hand hygiene compliance has become a global health challenge Lotfinejad N., et. al. (2020).

The prevention and control of COVID-19 and hand hygiene

It is currently believed that novel Coronavirus SARS-COV-2 is mainly transmitted through respiratory tract and physical contact, and has the possibility of aerosol transmission when exposed to high concentration of aerosol for a long time in a relatively enclosed space Jiajia, L., et. al. (2019). All the medical and health institutions regard the prevention and control of hospital infections of the novel coronavirus as an important task of hospital infection management. In this context, alcohol has become the essential ingredient of liquid soap and hand sanitizers in medical and health institutions due to its highly effectiveness of inactivation of coronavirus as well as its low cost, and it has been widely used in the five moments of hand hygiene among medical workers Lotfinejad N., et. al. (2020). However, investigations have shown that the frontline medical workers involved in treating the patients infected with novel coronavirus almost universally 97.0%(526/542) show symptoms related with preventative measures and characterized by dryness, descaling, and other forms of impaired skin barrier function Jiajia, L., et. al. (2019), which has a huge negative impact on their work.

Hand hygiene and impaired skin barrier

Occupational skin disease (OSD) has become the second most prevalent occupational disease in the world Erika W.C., et. al. (2016), most of which are diagnosed as occupational contact dermatitis including irritant and allergic contact dermatitis Zoi, P., et. al. (2018). Studies have found that washing hands 10 times a day at work can double the risk of hand dermatitis Maryam, S., et. al. (2019). Because medical workers need to cleanse and disinfect their hands frequently, the incidence of skin irritation among medical workers, especially nursing staffs, is higher than the average population (12%~30) Elaine, L et. al. (2006). Surveys show that 66.10% of frontline medical workers wash their hands more

than 10 times a day, but only 22.10% of respondents take skin care after hand washing, and 71.00% of respondents believe that damaged skin mainly manifests itself through common symptoms of impaired skin barrier similar to allergic reactions such as dryness and desquamation, erythematous papules, maceration, etc. Wolfgang, U., et. al. (2018). Irritating contact may be the key cause of occupational hand dermatitis Sara, B., et. al. (2019). A number of medical studies have confirmed that chlorhexidine and alcohol-based hand sanitizer in healthcare and disinfection products may cause contact dermatitis Morten O. S., et. al. (2016), Kristina I. S., et. al. (2016), Lindsey V.M., et. al. (2020), Kaori, Y., et. al. (2018).

Some scholars have studied the allergic ingredients in cleaning agents used by healthcare institutions, Table 1.

Table 1: Hypoallergenic ingredients in medical cleaning products low-Allergen
Medical Hand Skin Cleansers

Company	Product
Waterless skin soaps*	
3M Company	3M Avagard D Instant Hand Antiseptic with Moisturizers
B. Braun Medical, Inc	Promanum Pure
B. Braun Medical, Inc	Softa-Man Acute (Softalind 999)
B. Braun Medical, Inc	Softa-Man ViscoRub (Softalind ViscoRub)
BODE Chemie GmbH	Sterillium Med
BODE Chemie GmbH	Sterillium Classic pure
Diversey	Soft Care Liquid Instant Hand Sanitizer
Procter & Gamble	Safeguard Hand Sanitizer Gel
Company	
Steris Corporation	Soft 'N Sure Foamed Antiseptic Handrub
The Clorox Company	Clorox Hand Sanitizer
Veltek Associates, Inc	DEC-Hand
Water-needed skin soaps†	
Gojo Industries, Inc	Provon Antimicrobial Foam Handwash
with 2% CHG	
Steris Corporation	Septisol NPD with Triclosan
Skin disinfectants†	
3M Company with Moisturizers	3MAvagard Surgical and Healthcare Personnel Hand Antiseptics
3M Company	3MAvagard—Chlorhexidine Gluconate and Alcohol Lotion
Kimberly-Clark	Bactoshield CHG 2% Surgical Scrub Corporation
Xttrium Laboratories Inc	Exidine 2%

*Products are free of ACDS Core 80 Allergens.

†Products are free of ACDS Core 80 Allergens with published positive patch test reaction rates of greater than 1%.

The significance of moisturizers for skin barrier repair

Using skin moisturizers such as hand cream and moisturizing cream, etc. is undoubtedly the most convenient and effective way for medical workers to protect the skin barrier Claire H. L., et. al. (2016). The use of skin moisturizer can effectively repair the epidermal barrier and relieve skin symptoms such as redness, itching and dryness. Several countries have highlighted the importance of moisturizers for skin barriers and incorporated hand care into the standard prevention of occupational irritant hand dermatitis: use moisturizers at least 4 times a day after getting up, during lunch break, after work and before going to bed, and keep them on the skin for 30 minutes Madan I., et. al. (2020), Maryanne, M., et. al. (2017), Fabrizio, S., et. al. (2018). It is very important and necessary to apply moisturizer in time after hand cleansing each time. Many medical workers do not apply moisturizer after hand cleansing, usually because of operational requirements or busy work. They do not take care of their hands after hand cleansing each time, or they think that only one or two times of care every day is not going to be helpful. Although the effectiveness of moisturizers depends to a certain extent on suitable skin and compliance with regular use, studies have shown that one time use of creams containing ceramides can significantly improve cuticle water and condition and repair the skin barrier within 12-24 hours Stephanie N. J., et. al. (2020). M 's Loden M., et. al. (2020) experiment proved that the skin would lose the moisturizer that was applied onto it after getting contact with other substances, and only about 50% of the moisturizer remained on the skin surface 8 hours after its application. So it's important to reuse moisturizers every day to have certain effects. Applying moisturizer only once a day won't have a long-term effect, but applying it twice a day for a week will continue to protect the skin barrier seven days after cessation. So even if moisturizer cannot be applied every time after hand cleansing, it is still significant to apply it twice a day continuously for the moisturizing of the skin barrier. Enhancing hand skin care and preventing and improving skin barrier damage can increase the hand cleansing compliance among medical workers and improve the effectiveness of prevention and control of hospital infection.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Hand hygiene is the most convenient, economical and effective way to prevent cross-infection no matter it is SARS in 2003 or COVID-19 in 2020 or the daily work of medical workers. However, because medical staff need to frequently cleanse their hands over a long period of time, and they often cannot provide timely care to the skin after hand cleansing, microbe and cuticle cells on the surface of the damaged skin can be damaged and the immune function of skin can also be sabotaged, causing impaired skin barrier. When skin barrier function is damaged, symbiotic bacteria such as bacteria, fungi and viruses on the skin surface usually do not cause disease. But after entering dermis, it is easy to induce inflammation. However, the repair effect of moisturizers on the skin barrier has been widely confirmed clinically, and they are increasingly used in atopic dermatitis, eczema, psoriasis and other diseases related with impaired skin barrier. Considering the practical situation of prevention and combat against the epidemic, it is very important and necessary for medical workers to improve the hand skin care, protect the skin barrier and enhance the skin immunity. However, recently there have also been reports about allergic reactions caused by moisturizers. Therefore, in addition to considering the moisturizing effects and the tolerance to cleaning, the choice of moisturizers should also consider adverse reactions such as allergies.

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REFERENCES

- Barnes S., Stuart R., Redley B. (2019). "Health care worker sensitivity to chlorhexidine-based hand hygiene solutions: A cross-sectional survey". *Am J. Infect Control*, 47: 933-937.
- David B. J, Nathan McK.T, Rosen L. F. (2019). "Does Adherence to World Health Organization Hand Hygiene Protocols in the Operating Room Have the Potential to Produce Irritant Contact Dermatitis in Anesthesia Providers? *Anesth. Analg*", undefined.
- Giovana G. M, Gabrielli, B., Amante, M.H. (2017). "The pH of the main Brazilian commercial moisturizers and liquid soaps: considerations on the repair of the skin barrier. *An Bras Dermatol*", 92: 736-738.
- Higgins C. L, Palmer A. M, Cahill J. L. (2016). "Occupational skin disease among Australian healthcare workers: a retrospective analysis from an occupational dermatology clinic, 1993-2014". *Contact Derm.*, 75: 213-22.
- Ibler K. S, Jemec G. B. E, Garvey L. H. (2016). "Prevalence of delayed-type and immediate-type hypersensitivity in healthcare workers with hand eczema". *Contact Derm.*, 75: 223-9.
- Johannes, W., Alexandra, G., Reinhard N.H. (2018). "Lipids in the Skin and Ph". *Curr. Probl. Dermatol*, 54: 64-70.
- Jürgen, B., Peter, S. (2018). "The Relation of pH and Skin Cleansing". *Curr. Probl. Dermatol*, 54: 132-142.
- K. I, Shehu Nathan Y, Pires D. (2020). "Assessment of hand hygiene facilities and staff compliance in a large tertiary health care facility in northern Nigeria: a cross sectional study". *Antimicrob Resist. Infect Control*, 9: 30.
- Lan J., Song Z., Miao X. (2019). "Skin damage among healthcare workers managing coronavirus disease" *J. Am. Acad. Dermatol*, undefined.
- Larson E., Girard R., Pessoa-Silva C. L. (2006). "Skin reactions related to hand hygiene and selection of hand hygiene products". *Am J. Infect Control*, 34: 627-35.
- Lindsey V. M, Schlarbaum J. P., Hylwa S. A. (2020)." Allergenic Ingredients in Health Care Hand Sanitizers in the United States". *Dermatitis*, undefined.
- Loden M., Maibach HI. (2000). *Dry Skin and Moisturizers Chemistry and Function*. Washington DC: CRC Press.
- Lotfinejad N, Peters A., Pittet D. (2020). "Hand hygiene and the novel coronavirus pandemic: The role of healthcare workers". *J. Hosp. Infect.*, undefined.10.1016/j.jhin.2020.03.017.
- Madan I, Parsons V, Ntani G. (2020). "A behaviour change package to prevent hand dermatitis in nurses working in the National Health Service: results of a cluster randomized controlled trial". *Br. J. Dermatol*, undefined.
- María M.C. B, Emilio, R., Raúl M.G. (2019). "Hand Hygiene Teaching Strategies among Nursing Staff: A Systematic Review". *Int J. Environ Res Public Health*, 16: undefined.
- Maryanne, McG. Govednik J. (2017)." Irritant Contact Dermatitis on Hands". *Am J Med Qual*, 32: 93-99.
- Neesha, R. (2020). "Effective hand hygiene-wash your hands and reduce the risk". *Br. J. Nurs.*, 29: 10.
- Opstrup M. S., Johansen J. D., Zachariae C. (2016). "Contact allergy to chlorhexidine in a tertiary dermatology clinic in Denmark". *Contact Derm.*, 74: 29-36.
- Papadatou Z., Williams H., Cooper K.B. (2018). "Effectiveness of interventions for preventing occupational irritant hand dermatitis: a quantitative systematic review". *JBIC Database System Rev. Implement Rep.*, 16: 1398-1417.
- Qian, Z., Yang Miles M., Huang Y.Y. (2018). "How to make hand hygiene interventions more attractive to nurses: A discrete choice experiment". *PLoS ONE*, 13: e0202014.

- Soltanipoor M., Rustemeyer T., Sluiter J.K. (2019). "Evaluating the effect of electronic monitoring and feedback on hand cream use in healthcare workers: Healthy Hands Project". *Contact Derm.*, 80: 26-34.
- Soltanipoor M., Kezic S., Sluiter J. K. (2017). "The effectiveness of a skin care program for the prevention of contact dermatitis in health care workers (the Healthy Hands Project): study protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial". *Trials*, 18: 92.
- Soltanipoor M., Rustemeyer T., Sluiter J. K. (2019). "Evaluating the effect of electronic monitoring and feedback on hand cream use in healthcare workers: Healthy Hands Project". *Contact Derm.*, 80: 26-34.
- Spada F., Barnes Tanya M., Greive K. A. (2018). "Skin hydration is significantly increased by a cream formulated to mimic the skin's own natural moisturizing systems". *Clin. Cosmet Investig Dermatol*, 11: 491-497.
- Stephanie N. J, Dykes P., Snatchfold J. (2020). "Single application of lamellar moisturizers provides significantly increased hydration of the stratum corneum for up to 24 hours in a randomized trial". *J. Cosmet Dermatol*, undefined.
- Tartari E, Muthukumar P, Peters A. (2019). "Monitoring your institution: the WHO hand hygiene self-assessment framework-is it worth it?" *Clin. Microbiol. Infect*, 25: 925-928.
- Von Grote E. C, Palaniswamy K., Meckfessel M. H. (2016). "Managing Occupational Irritant Contact Dermatitis Using a Two-Step Skincare Regimen Designed to Prevent Skin Damage and Support Skin Recovery". *J. Drugs Dermatol*, 15: 1504-1510.
- Yonezawa K., Megumi, H., Masayo M. (2018). "Effects of moisturizing skincare on skin barrier function and the prevention of skin problems in 3-month-old infants: A randomized controlled trial." *J. Dermatol.*, 45: 24-30.
- WHO. How does COVID-19 Spread? Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/q-a-detail/q-a-coronaviruses>. (Accessed 26 March 2020).
- Wolfgang, U., Bauer A., Bensefa-Colas L. (2018). "Extended documentation for hand dermatitis patients: Pilot study on irritant exposures. *Contact Derm.*, 79: 168-174.